

Disease reactions 15 and 35 DAI. Faizabad District, U.P., India.

Representative test varieties	Disease-score ^a		Type of reaction ^b	Varieties (no.)
	15 DAI	35 DAI		
Anjani III, Bishunbhog, Damodar, IR20, Randhuri, Zeerabatti	1	1	R	7
Chinidardi, Dehradun (Mota), Dhurigabha, Gallor, Gajraj, Kala Namak	1	3	MR (SB)	11
Katri, Loungchoor, Rambhog, Saraya, Sita, Surajpankhi 374	3	3	MR	10
Chameli	1	5	MS (VSB)	1
Beni, Benideoria, Gaurea, Mutmuri, Pankhali, Shyamzsera	3	5	MS (SB)	24
Adamchini, Amgandh, Badshah Pasand, Bhagalpuri, Ramjas	5	5	MS	29
Agwar, Bilaspur, Delha, Dadhaha, Sonachoor, FRG10	3	7	S (VSB)	6
Ashahniya, Basahwa, Dudaha, Jaisuria, Lalkibhadai, Sumokhan	5	7	S (SB)	13
Bajri, Bakki, Karhan, Kotabasmati, Mirchbooti, Motibadam	7	7	S	13
Champa (C), Kalamdan, Mutra, Sukhwan, Tinpakhiya, Agtahwa (FD)	5	9	HS (VSB)	9
Gheebhat, Kalakand, Karnya, Kashi P.D., Madhukar, Ramkajra	7	9	HS (SB)	11
Anand, Anjana, Bindibali, Bindikali, Gajgaur, TN1	9	9	HS	30

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1980). ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible, SB = slow blighting, VSB = very slow blighting.

infection within 15 DAI; others took more time (see table).

The results indicate the limitations of recording observations only at 15 DAI. It is possible to divide reaction groups into normal blighting, slow blighting, and very slow blighting varieties. □

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Insect resistance

Incorporation of brown planthopper (BPH) resistance genes from indica into japonica rice

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None of the 8,200 japonica varieties or lines we screened in 1976-82 were resistant to BPH. Resistance genes can only be found in the tall traditional indica varieties of South Asia. We transferred BPH resistance genes from indica to two japonica lines (80047 and 80079) in 1980. Using those lines as resistance sources, several promising japonica lines resistant to BPH have been developed (see table).

- 864 derived from Yan Keng 2//791943/80047 yields 8 t/ha, 10% more than widely grown Yan Keng 2 and is suitable for single and double cropping in the Chang Jiang River

Yield performance and insect resistance of promising japonica lines. Jiangsu, China, 1987.

Line	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./ plant)	Grains (no./ panicle)	Sterility (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Resistance		
								BPH	BB	BI
864	147	100-105	9	120	8	26.0	8.0	MR	R	R
870064	155	90-95	9	146	14.2	25.3	7.9	R	R	R
850041	150	95-100	8	116	24.0	23.0	7.0	R	R	MR

basin. It is resistant to bacterial blight (BB) and moderately resistant to BPH and blast (BI). Its grain quality is acceptable to consumers.

- 870664 (Yan Keng 2//791943/80047//Non Ken 57/IR26) yields 8 t/ha and is suitable for the Tai-hu Lake basin and the

Chang Jiang River basin. It is resistant to BPH, BI, and BB.

- 850041 derived from 791943/80047 has large panicles, but unsatisfactory lodging resistance. Average yields are 7 t/ha. It is highly resistant to BPH and BB, but susceptible to sheath blight. □

Screening rice seedlings for resistance to leafhopper (LF)

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We screened 26 accessions from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project at the seedling stage for

resistance to LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* in the 1987 wet season.

Pregerminated seeds were sown 6 cm apart in 50- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedboxes. Six rows of each accession were planted across the width of the seedbox, for 3 plants/hill, 5 hills/row. One row of susceptible check TN1 and one row of resistant check Ptb 33 were sown at random in each seedbox.

Seedboxes were transferred to iron trays (60 × 40 × 15 cm) filled with 5 cm water 7 d after seeding (DAS). The boxes were covered with nylon net cages 20 DAS and 10 moth pairs/cage released in each cage. (A cotton swab soaked in 1% sugar solution was hung inside the cage as food for the moths.)

Moths were allowed to oviposit 3-4 d. LF damage was assessed 15 d after release of moths.

The same accessions were screened in microplots (2 × 2 m).

TNAULFR831324, 832042, 842718, 842735, and 842745 exhibited good resistance in the greenhouse and in the microplots (see table). □

Reaction of rice seedlings to LF. Coimbatore, India, 1987 wet season.

Accession	Cross	Damage rating ^a	
		Greenhouse	Microplot
TNAULFR831324	Bhavani/IR4707-106-3-2	3	3
TNAULFR832042	Bhavani/ARC10550	3	5
TNAULFR842718	Bhavani/ARC10550	3	3
TNAULFR842735	Bhavani/IR4707-106-3-2	3	5
TNAULFR842745	Bhavani/IR4707-106-3-2	3	5
Balam (donor)	—	3	5
RP2430-350-54	Rasi/Chittaraikar	5	5
RP2430-361-3	Rasi/Chittaraikar	5	5
RP2430-372-75	Rasi/Chittaraikar	5	5
ARC11281 (donor)	—	5	5
Choorapundy (donor)	—	5	5
TN1 (susceptible check)	DGWW/Tsai-Yuan-Chan	9	9
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	—	3	3

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Field incidence of and host resistance to Angoumois grain moth (AGM)

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We surveyed field incidence of AGM *Sitotroga cerealella* O. on rice in the field at the Agricultural College in Madurai and the Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute in Aduthurai. Seed samples of 100 g for each variety were collected in polythepe bags and adult moth emergence monitored for 6 wk.

AGM emerged from 124 of 213 samples at Madurai and from 59 of 151 samples at Aduthurai. Incidence was highest in IR and CO varieties; IR20, IR50, IR54, IR64, CO 25, CO 31, CO 37, CO 42, CO 43, CO 44, ACM11, ACM12, IET7254, ADT36, AD85003, NLR9672, Ponni, TNAU801790, TNAU831293, TNAU831520, and TNAU831521 showed field infestation in both places.

We evaluated 38 CO varieties for resistance on the basis of number of moths emerging, percentage infested grains, weight loss, and weight of adult moths; 15 were resistant.

Resistant CO 1, CO 27, and CO 32; moderately resistant CO 40; moderately susceptible CO 42; and highly

Physical and biochemical characters of rices resistant to Angoumois grain moth in India.

Variety	Husk ^a thickness (cm)	Physical characters			Biochemical factors		
		Grain hardness ^a (alkali value)	Length: breadth ratio ^b	100-grain weight ^c (g)	Silica, content ^d (%)	Total protein ^d (%)	Total amylose ^d (%)
CO 32	0.031	2	4.0	1.8	18.9	5.9	23.9
CO 21	0.037	2	3.5	2.0	19.1	9.8	28.9
CO 1	0.032	1	3.1	2.1	17.9	9.2	24.5
CO 40	0.027	4	2.0	2.3	16.8	8.2	20.7
CO 42	0.019	3	2.7	2.1	16.8	6.5	19.9
CO 43	0.017	4	2.1	1.9	15.1	6.5	19.4
CO 44	0.014	5	1.9	1.9	15.1	7.6	21.9

^aMean of 10 observations. ^bMean of 15 observations. ^cMean of 3 replications. ^dMean of 2 replications.

susceptible CO 43 and CO 44 were selected to study factors conferring resistance.

Husk thickness, grain hardness (alkali value), length-breadth ratio (grain fineness), 100-grain weight, and silica,

protein, and amylose content were analyzed. In general, resistant varieties had thick husk, low alkali value, coarse grain, higher 100-grain weight, and high silica, total protein, and total amylose content (see table). □

Excess water tolerance

Breeding for submergence tolerance

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In eastern India, rice seedlings are likely to be submerged 30-40 d after transplanting when the monsoon breaks

in mid-Jun. We studied FR13A, FR43B, and CN540, their two hybrids, and susceptible check IR20 for submergence tolerance and recovery.

Initial height and leaf and tiller number of 10-, 30-, and 40-d-old seedlings were recorded, and seedlings were submerged in either 30 or 60 cm deep water. Survival percentage, height and leaf number were taken, and